

STAGES OF THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN WORLD LANGUAGES

Normurodova Sokhiba Mallaevna

Assistant teacher Department of Languages, Samarkand State
Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11402659>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th April 2024

Accepted: 28th May 2024

Published: 31st May 2024

KEYWORDS

language device,
Romance languages, lexical
unit, classical period, dialect.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the emergence of the Latin language, the stages of its historical development, and its origin. In addition, detailed information on the role and importance of the Latin language in world languages is given.

Introduction

The Latin language, or *Lingua Latina*, belongs to the Latino - the Falis subgroup of the Italian branch of the Indo-European language family, along with the Falisian and Siglarsky, and is one of the most ancient languages, as well as the only Italian language used. The Latin language, as the progenitor of all languages of the Romanesque branch, had a significant impact on the formation of the current English, French, Spanish and Italian languages.

As an example of borrowing in the above language systems, we note the following lexical feature of the word "language": lat. - *Lingua*, Spanish. - *Lengua*, English. - *Language*, Fran. - *Langu*; Or, for example, "table": lat. - *mēnsa*, Fran. - *Table* (from lat. *Tabula* - board), Spanish. - *Mesa*. The Romanesque languages inherited not only the generality of the lexical and morphological, but also the infinitive constructions of the Latin language. Currently, Latin does not lose its relevance not only in the system of humanitarian and natural sciences in the form of educational discipline, but also in the usual life of people whose activities are not related to scientific research, such as representatives of youth who often use winged Latin sayings in social networks or oral speech; Or the slogans of companies that also use Latin turns of speech.

Results and discussion

However, the modern Latin pronunciation is significantly changed and greatly different from the classical one, which determines some misunderstanding and bias of representatives of one or another dialect, in other words, the language barrier. In general, the types of pronunciations of modern Latin are divided into: original (or classic), Italonized, English and germanized. The difference in pronunciation is explained by the territorial position of an individual studying the Latin language and, as a result, a dialectical feature of his speech. Thus, in the Russian educational structure, often the Germanized form of Latin is considered, used

in medical terminology, and the italicized pronunciation is assigned the position of the liturgical language of the Roman Catholic Church, the center of which is the city-state of the Vatican, where the Latin language, along with Italian, has the status of an official.

The history of the formation of the Latin language originates from ancient Italy, where Latin developed as the language of the people of the Latins (Latin Latini), which was important for further romance (lat. Romanus). Traditionally, the following stages of Latin development are distinguished. The archaic stage (until the 1st century (75) n. E.). Latin quickly modifies under the influence of Greek and Etruscan languages, the first Latin inscriptions appear. The most famous representatives of the archaic period were ancient Roman comedias Titus Mazius Plaut (250-184 BC), Publius Terentius Afron (190-159 BC) and poet-playwright Quintus Ennius (239 - 169 BC), whose works have come to date. The classic stage (from the 1st century BC to the I. to the 1st century, e.).

The formation of Latin here had a significant impact by the status of Rome, who was the center of the Locations, now: the central city of the Roman state, a strong slave -owned power. The classical stage of the history of the Latin language includes the stage of the formation of classical Latin, used by citizens of Rome, which is also applied to the literary Latin language. This period is distinguished by the works of such famous literary figures and philosophers as: Cicero, Virgil, Titus Lucretius Kar. In the future, the Latin language system will not tolerate significant changes, up to the medieval era (500 g. - 1300) and the fall of the Roman Empire, where the Latin language, more and more changed under the influence of other ethnic languages, will be rooted as the church language of liturgical treatises and works, in the education system and other aspects of social life.

In the Renaissance era (1300 - 1600), Latin acquires a special status. The revival is the time of the predominance of anthropocentrism and humanism, scientific discoveries and the development of the spiritual sphere of society. The Renaissance, along with the revival of the art of antiquity, revived interest in Latin. The Latin language in the era of revival becomes the most important means of scientific and cultural communication. [1] In the era of the New Age (1600 - 1900), which has changed the revival, Latin is already used, in particular, in scientific publications, documents of legal, diplomatic and religious nature. Isaac Newton wrote his works in Latin (1643 - 1727), Rene Descartes (1596 - 1650), Mikhail Vasilievich Lomonosov (1711 - 1765), Francis Bacon (1561 - 1626 G.) and others.

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Currently, there are organizations whose activities are aimed at popularizing the Latin language. An example is the movement "Living Latin" (Latinitas Viva) - an international unification of people using colloquial Latin as a means of communication. Under the auspices of this movement, the Vox Latina International magazine is published. In Germany - Latinitas magazine, where Latin works are printed. There are many musical groups that use the Latin language in the texts of the songs, for example, the German metal is the Powerwolf group, the folk is the Corvus Corax group, called from the Latin designation of the Vorona-General; Haggard, performing symphony metal, etc. The value of the Latin language in our time is determined by the need to know it with any specialist in both natural-scientific areas and humanitarian.

Conclusion

Latin also has a significant role for a scientist - a historian studying one or another period of the European era, for example, medieval; And for a biologist, since Latin is used in a medical nomenclature. The need for Latin is also justified for a philologist, because the Latin language simplifies the study of the languages of the Romanesque branch because of its similarity to

their phonetic, lexical and grammatical structure. Many Latinisms are used in Russian, for example: surname - (Familia), Ego, I - (EGO), student - (Studeo (diligently engaged)).

The Latin language has passed the stage of its formation from the era of antiquity to our time, again losing and gaining its relevance. But, although he has not retained the status of an interethnic language, Latin still plays an important role in the modern world.

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